

TECHNOLOGIES OF RECOMMENDATION SYSTEM

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Abstract: Systems implementing a content-based recommendation approach analyze a set of documents and/or descriptions of items previously rated by a user, and build a model or profile of user interests based on the features of the objects rated by that user. The profile is a structured representation of user interests, adopted to recommend new interesting items. The recommendation process basically consists in matching up the attributes of the user profile against the attributes of a content object. The result is a relevance judgment that represents the user's level of interest in that object. If a profile accurately reflects user preferences, it is of tremendous advantage for the effectiveness of an information access process. For instance, it could be used to filter search results by deciding whether a user is interested in a specific Web page or not and, in the negative case, preventing it from being displayed.

Key words: content-based, content analyzer, profile learner, filtering component, like/dislike, active user, ratings, text comments, profile.

Introduction

The abundance of information available on the Web and in Digital Libraries, in combination with their dynamic and heterogeneous nature, has determined a rapidly increasing difficulty in finding what we want when we need it and in a manner which best meets our requirements.

As a consequence, the role of user modeling and personalized information access is becoming crucial: users need a personalized support in sifting through large amounts of available information, according to their interests and tastes.

Many information sources embody recommender systems as a way of personalizing their content for users. Recommender systems have the effect of guiding users in a personalized way to interesting or useful objects in a large space of possible options. Recommendation algorithms use input about a customer's interests to generate a list of recommended items. At Amazon.com, recommendation algorithms are used to personalize the online store for each customer, for example showing programming titles to a software engineer and baby toys to a new mother.

The problem of recommending items has been studied extensively, and two main paradigms have emerged. Content-based recommendation systems try to recommend items similar to those a given user has liked in the past, whereas systems designed according to the collaborative recommendation paradigm identify users whose preferences are similar to those of the given user and recommend items they have liked.

A High Level Architecture of Content-based Systems

Content-based Information Filtering (IF) systems need proper techniques for representing the items and producing the user profile, and some strategies for comparing the user profile with the item representation. The high level architecture of a content-based recommender system is depicted in Figure 1. The recommendation process is performed in three steps, each of which is handled by a separate component:

- **CONTENT ANALYZER** – When information has no structure (e.g. text), some kind of pre-processing step is needed to extract structured relevant information. The main responsibility of the component is to represent the content of items (e.g. documents, Web pages, news, product descriptions, etc.) coming from information sources in a form suitable for the next processing steps. Data items are analyzed by feature extraction techniques in order to shift item representation from the original information space to the target one (e.g. Web pages represented as keyword vectors). This representation is the input to the **PROFILE LEARNER and FILTERING COMPONENT**;

• **PROFILE LEARNER** – This module collects data representative of the user preferences and tries to generalize this data, in order to construct the user profile. Usually, the generalization strategy is realized through machine learning techniques, which are able to infer a model of user interests starting from items liked or disliked in the past. For instance, the **PROFILE LEARNER** of a Web page recommender can implement a relevance feedback method in which the learning technique combines vectors of positive and negative examples into a prototype vector representing the user profile. Training examples are Web pages on which a positive or negative feedback has been provided by the user;

• **FILTERING COMPONENT** – This module exploits the user profile to suggest relevant items by matching the profile representation against that of items to be recommended. The result is a binary or continuous relevance judgment (computed using some similarity metrics), the latter case resulting in a ranked list of potentially interesting items. In the above mentioned example, the matching is realized by computing the cosine similarity between the prototype vector and the item vectors.

Fig. 1: High level architecture of a Content-based Recommender

The first step of the recommendation process is the one performed by the **CONTENT ANALYZER**, that usually borrows techniques from Information

Retrieval systems. Item descriptions coming from Information Source are processed by the CONTENT ANALYZER, that extracts features (keywords, n-grams, concepts, ...) from unstructured text to produce a structured item representation, stored in the repository Represented Items.

In order to construct and update the profile of the active user *ua* (user for which recommendations must be provided) her reactions to items are collected in some way and recorded in the repository Feedback. These reactions, called annotations or feedback, together with the related item descriptions, are exploited during the process of learning a model useful to predict the actual relevance of newly presented items. Users can also explicitly define their areas of interest as an initial profile without providing any feedback.

Typically, it is possible to distinguish between two kinds of relevance feedback: positive information (inferring features liked by the user) and negative information.

Two different techniques can be adopted for recording user's feedback. When a system requires the user to explicitly evaluate items, this technique is usually referred to as "explicit feedback"; the other technique, called "implicit feedback", does not require any active user involvement, in the sense that feedback is derived from monitoring and analyzing user's activities.

Explicit evaluations indicate how relevant or interesting an item is to the user. There are three main approaches to get explicit relevance feedback:

- like/dislike – items are classified as "relevant" or "not relevant" by adopting a simple binary rating scale;
- ratings – a discrete numeric scale is usually adopted to judge items. Alternatively, symbolic ratings are mapped to a numeric scale, such as in Syskill & Webert, where users have the possibility of rating a Web page as hot, lukewarm, or cold;
- text comments – Comments about a single item are collected and presented to the users as a means of facilitating the decision-making process,. For instance, customer's feedback at Amazon.com or eBay.com might help users in deciding whether an item has been appreciated by the community. Textual comments are

helpful, but they can overload the active user because she must read and interpret each comment to decide if it is positive or negative, and to what degree. The literature proposes advanced techniques from the affective computing research area to make content-based recommenders able to automatically perform this kind of analysis.

Explicit feedback has the advantage of simplicity, albeit the adoption of numeric/symbolic scales increases the cognitive load on the user, and may not be adequate for catching user's feeling about items. Implicit feedback methods are based on assigning a relevance score to specific user actions on an item, such as saving, discarding, printing, bookmarking, etc. The main advantage is that they do not require a direct user involvement, even though biasing is likely to occur, e.g. interruption of phone calls while reading.

In order to build the profile of the active user u_a , the training set T_{Ra} for u_a must be defined. T_{Ra} is a set of pairs $\langle I_k, r_k \rangle$, where r_k is the rating provided by u_a on the item representation I_k . Given a set of item representation labeled with ratings, the PROFILE LEARNER applies supervised learning algorithms to generate a predictive model – the user profile – which is usually stored in a profile repository for later use by the FILTERING COMPONENT. Given a new item representation, the FILTERING COMPONENT predicts whether it is likely to be of interest for the active user, by comparing features in the item representation to those in the representation of user preferences (stored in the user profile). Usually, the FILTERING COMPONENT implements some strategies to rank potentially interesting items according to the relevance with respect to the user profile. Top-ranked items are included in a list of recommendations L_a , that is presented to u_a . User tastes usually change in time, therefore up-to-date information must be maintained and provided to the PROFILE LEARNER in order to automatically update the user profile. Further feedback is gathered on generated recommendations by letting users state their satisfaction or dissatisfaction with items in L_a . After gathering that feedback, the learning process is performed again on the new training set, and the resulting profile is adapted to the updated user interests. The iteration of

the feedback-learning cycle over time allows the system to take into account the dynamic nature of user preferences.

Conclusion

In this article we surveyed the field of content-based recommender systems, by providing an overview of the most important aspects characterizing that kind of systems. Although there is a bunch of recommender systems in different domains, they share in common a means for representing items to be recommended and user profiles. The paper discusses the main issues related to the representation of items, starting from simple techniques for representing structured data, to more complex techniques coming from the Information Retrieval research area for unstructured data. We analyzed the main content recommender systems developed in the last 15 years, by highlighting the reasons for which a more complex “semantic analysis” of content is needed in order to go beyond the syntactic evidence of user interests provided by keywords. A review of the main strategies (and systems) adopted to introduce some semantics in the recommendation process is carried out, by providing evidence of the leading role of linguistic knowledge, even if a more specific knowledge is mandatory for a deeper understanding and contextualization of the user interests in different application domains. The latest issues in advanced text representation using sources of world knowledge, such as Wikipedia, have been highlighted, albeit they have not yet used in the context of learning user profiles. In order to complete the survey, a variety of learning algorithms have been described as well.

References

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